

Investigating the Effect of Number of Needle for Lock and Chain Stitches on Seam Strength in 100% Cotton Twill Gabardine Fabrics

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ABSTRACT

Seam strength is a vital factor influencing the durability and performance of garments. Among the various stitching techniques used in garment manufacturing, lock stitch and chain stitch are the most commonly employed to ensure seam integrity. Although prior studies have examined how stitch type and fabric affect seam strength, the influence of needle number has not been extensively studied. Understanding this effect is crucial for optimizing garment quality and production efficiency. This study examined how the number of needles impacts the seam strength of lock and chain stitches in 100% cotton twill gabardine fabric. The selected fabric was characterized by an ends per inch (EPI) of 126, picks per inch (PPI) of 58, a warp yarn count of 21 Ne, and a weft yarn count of 17 Ne. Fabric specimens were prepared according to the ISO 13935-2 standard. Stitching was performed using a universal sharp-point sewing needle sized 90/14 and a polyester core-spun thread with a ticket number of 40 (60 Tex). Both single and double-needle techniques were applied across lock stitch and chain stitch configurations. Seam strength was evaluated using a universal seam strength tester (Titan). Results demonstrated that double-needle stitched seams exhibited greater strength compared to single-needle seams in both warp and weft directions. Notably, the strength enhancement with double-needle stitching was not proportional to needle doubling, presenting increases of 18–27% in the warp direction and 8–11% in the weft direction. Failure analysis revealed seam rupture predominantly occurred near fabric edges stitched by the first needle, thereby constraining the reinforcing contribution of the second needle. These findings suggest that although double-needle stitching enhances seam strength, the benefits are relatively modest when balanced against increased production complexity and costs. Thus, manufacturers should consider these trade-offs when selecting stitching techniques to optimize seam performance and operational efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality and performance of garments are closely tied to the structural integrity of their seams, which is primarily determined by stitch and seam types, sewing parameters, and the interaction between sewing threads and fabrics [1–3]. Seam

strength plays an important part in determining garment durability, especially for those applications related to high stress, because poor seam performance can render a garment unsuitable even if the fabric remains intact [4–6]. Of the sewing parameters that will influence seam quality,

needle multiplicity has become important for seam performance, particularly with lockstitch and chain stitch methods [7]. While numerous studies have been performed on the optimization of seam strength, few specifically address the contribution made by needle type to seam strength during the sewing of tightly woven 100% cotton twill gabardine fabric.

Stitches, defined as the interlocking of sewing threads within fabric, provide the structural framework for seams, while seam construction determines the garment's durability, aesthetic appeal, and functional serviceability [8]. Lockstitches, characterized by their two-thread interlocking mechanism, are widely used for their strong and stable seams, whereas chain stitches, utilizing looped threads, offer higher elasticity and adaptability to fabric extensibility [9–11]. The number of needles involved in these stitching processes can greatly influence seam strength due to the change in thread tension distribution, stitch density, and fabric distortion tendencies [12]. This paper investigates these parameters for 100% cotton twill gabardine, one of the strong fabrics usually applied in formal and workwear apparel because of its durability and resistance to wrinkles [14].

Seam quality extends beyond strength and encompasses attributes like elasticity, slippage resistance, and visual consistency, which are influenced by fabric weave, stitch type, and sewing parameters [15-17]. Cotton twill gabardine, with its tight weave and inherent strength, presents unique challenges in sewing, such as needle penetration resistance and seam puckering risks [18]. Changes in needle multiplicity can alleviate or worsen these issues through the re-distribution of stress and interaction with fabrics during sewing [19]. In addition, the mechanical properties of sewing threads, such as tensile strength and elongation, play an important role in seam performance improvement in different configurations of needles [20].

Current studies have indicated that sewing parameters such as stitch density, thread type, and seam type need to be optimized in order to ensure the highest garment quality [21-24]. However,

most of the studies lack the focus on the impacts caused by needle multiplicity on seam strength for lock and chain stitches in densely woven fabrics like twill gabardine. This paper tries to fill this gap by providing an understanding of the relationship between needle configurations and seam performance, hence giving practical recommendations that can be used to enhance garment durability and production efficiency.

In this work, therefore, an attempt has been made to study the effects of needle multiplicity on seam strength for lock and chain stitches in 100% cotton twill gabardine fabrics for the superimposed seam, which is the most commonly used seam in any woven garment. The results are expected to add to the existing literature on sewing dynamics and help apparel manufacturers improve the quality of their products with optimal sewing parameters.

2. MATERIALS & METHOD

2.1 Material Preparation

In this study, a 100% cotton twill gabardine fabric was selected, characterized by an ends per inch (EPI) of 126, picks per inch (PPI) of 58, warp yarn count of 21 Ne, and weft yarn count of 17 Ne. A universal sharp-point needle with a size of 90/14 (European/US sizing) and a polyester core-spun sewing thread with a ticket number of 40 (60 Tex) were employed for the experimental procedures. Fabric specimens were meticulously prepared in accordance with the ISO 13935-2 standard. The investigation incorporated four stitching variations involving two stitching techniques with differing needle counts: Single Needle Lock Stitch (SNLS) conforming to ISO 301, Double Needle Lock Stitch (DNLS) conforming to ISO 301-2, Single Needle Chain Stitch (SNCS) conforming to ISO 401, and Double Needle Chain Stitch (DNCS) conforming to ISO 401-2. Throughout the experimentation, critical parameters including stitches per inch (SPI), sewing thread count, and seam types were maintained consistently to ensure comparability of results.

2.2 Method

This study assesses the seam strength of 100% cotton twill gabardine fabric in accordance with ISO 13935-2 standards. Fabric specimens were prepared by cutting rectangular pieces measuring

10 cm in width and 10 cm in length, each incorporating a 1 cm seam allowance. Seams were produced using lockstitch and chain stitch sewing machines configured with a superimposed seam design, maintaining a consistent stitch density of 15 stitches per inch (SPI). Seam classification adhered to ISO specifications, with class SSa1 designated for single-needle stitching and class SSa2 for double-needle stitching.

Figure 1: Sample preparation for seam strength measurement according to ISO 13935-2 method

Prior to testing, all fabric samples were conditioned for 24 hours in a controlled environment maintained at $20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65\% \pm 2\%$ relative humidity, in accordance with established textile testing protocols. Seam strength evaluations were performed using a universal testing machine (Titan), operating at a crosshead speed of 100 mm/min. Tensile force was applied progressively until seam failure occurred. The maximum load sustained at the point of failure was recorded, and seam strength values were expressed in Newtons (N). To ensure experimental consistency and reliability, each stitch type underwent quintuplicate testing, with meticulous records maintained throughout the process.

The resulting data, comprising seam strength measurements in both warp and weft directions, were systematically compiled and presented in detailed reports. Visual representations of the findings were provided through graphical illustrations, as shown in Figures 2 through 9.

Figure 2: Warp seam strength graph of SNLS (ISO 301)

Figure 3: Weft seam strength graph of SNLS (ISO 301)

Figure 4: Warp seam strength graph of DNLS (ISO 301-2)

Figure 5: Weft seam strength graph of DNLS (ISO 301-2)

Figure 6: Warp seam strength graph of SNCS (ISO 401)

Figure 7: Weft seam strength graph of SNCS (ISO 401)

Figure 8: Warp seam strength graph of DNCS (ISO 401-2)

Figure 9: Weft seam strength graph of DNCS (ISO 401-2)

3. RESULT & DISCUSSION

3.1 RESULT

In this research, seam strength of different stitches having different thread number have been analyzed. The results are summarized below:

Table 4: Comparative study on seam strength based on the number of needle on Lock and Chain stitches

Sewing Machine Type	Stitch Type	Experiment Number	Seam Strength (N)	Coefficient Limit	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation (CV%)	Avg. seam strength (N)	Direction
Single Needle Lock Stitch	ISO 301	01	206.10	±17.38	14.02	6.842	204.91	Warp
		02	225.35					
		03	208.59					
		04	196.31					
		05	188.19					
Double Needle Lock Stitch	ISO 301-2	01	246.16	±19.81	15.98	6.626	241.18	
		02	237.82					
		03	261.67					
		04	217.45					
		05	242.78					
Single Needle Chain Stitch	ISO 401	01	286.02	±37.49	30.24	11.47	263.56	
		02	232.06					
		03	230.66					
		04	274.53					
		05	294.52					
Double Needle Chain Stitch	ISO 401-2	01	333.76	±48.04	38.75	11.600	334.00	
		02	337.45					
		03	386.24					
		04	276.87					
		05	335.70					
Single Needle Lock Stitch	ISO 301	01	211.98	±29.88	24.11	11.72	205.70	Weft
		02	236.64					
		03	192.09					
		04	214.68					
		05	173.11					
Double Needle Lock Stitch	ISO 301-2	01	212.32	±14.09	11.36	5.148	220.76	
		02	212.94					
		03	213.52					
		04	227.21					
		05	237.79					
Single Needle Chain Stitch	ISO 401	01	252.28	±20.95	16.90	7.158	236.11	
		02	255.99					
		03	224.50					
		04	218.79					
		05	228.99					
Double Needle Chain Stitch	ISO 401-2	01	232.20	±27.98	22.57	8.622	261.74	
		02	289.12					
		03	277.12					
		04	261.87					

		05	248.40				
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Figure 10: Comparative study on seam strength based on the number of needles on Lock and Chain stitches

3.2 RESULT DISCUSSION

Table 1 and Figure 10 provide a comparative analysis of seam strength as influenced by the number of sewing needles used for both lock and chain stitches. For the warp direction, the average seam strength using a single needle lock stitch (SNLS, ISO 301) was measured at 204.91 N. This value increased to 241.18 N when a double needle lock stitch (DNLS, ISO 301-2) was used. In the weft direction, the average seam strength for SNLS was 205.7 N, which increased to 220.76 N with DNLS.

A similar trend was observed for chain stitches. For the warp direction, the average seam strength for a single needle chain stitch (SNCS, ISO 401) was 263.56 N, which saw a significant increase to 334 N when a double needle chain stitch (DNCS, ISO 401-2) was employed. In the weft direction, the average seam strength for SNCS was 236.11 N, increasing to 261.74 N with DNCS.

Overall, the highest seam strength values for both warp and weft were recorded for DNLS (ISO 301-2) and DNCS (ISO 401-2), while the lowest values were found in SNLS (ISO 301) and SNCS (ISO 401). When comparing the two stitching techniques, chain stitches consistently demonstrated higher seam strength values than lock stitches for both warp and weft directions.

The results indicate that increasing the number of needles generally enhances seam strength. However, the strength does not double when the

number of needles is doubled; instead, there is an observed increase of approximately 18-27% in the warp direction and 8-11% in the weft direction for both lock and chain stitches. Under applied load, the seam typically fails near the fabric edges, with the second line of stitches being only minimally affected.

4. CONCLUSION

Clothing manufacturers often prioritize seam appearance over its technical properties, yet seam performance is a critical determinant of garment quality. While single-thread lock and chain stitches are commonly used in garment construction, it is vital that these seams are sufficiently strong to endure the stresses of wear and tear. When high seam strength is required, increasing the number of sewing needles is advisable. Although double-needle stitches offer only a modest increase in seam strength compared to single-needle stitches, they are still recommended. Under stress, double-needle seams tend to break primarily at the fabric edges, with the secondary line of stitches remaining largely intact, thereby preventing the seam from fully opening. This study provides valuable guidance for selecting the appropriate number of needles for both lock and chain stitch types, based on specific product requirements, to ensure high garment quality.

5. LIMITATION AND FUTURE SCOPE:

The experiments were conducted within an operational garment industry, where the availability of time and resources was significantly constrained due to ongoing production activities. As a result, the number of samples tested and the range of variables analyzed were limited. Factory management restricted extended testing to avoid disruptions to their production schedule. Consequently, while this study provides initial insights, there remains substantial scope for future research involving a broader set of parameters and more comprehensive seam strength evaluations under varied conditions.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have confirmed that there is no conflict of interest with this work.

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